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The Representation of Musical Entertainment in Middle English Romances

Riassunto: Nei romanzi medievali l'intrattenimento musicale ha spesso un ruolo centrale, come ulteriore manifestazione del fasto della corte. Corni, tamburi e vielle, arpe, organi e cornamuse, risuonano nella sala creando un'atmosfera festosa. I diversi strumenti vengono menzionati in lunghe liste attentamente studiate per trasmettere un senso di magnificenza ed armonia. Se da un lato questi elenchi potrebbero essere stati utilizzati come figure di amplificazione, dall'altro potrebbero avere avuto anche una funzione narrativa. Il presente lavoro si propone quindi di analizzare la rappresentazione dell'intrattenimento musicale nei romanzi medio inglesi per capire se la scelta di specifici strumenti sia semplicemente finalizzata ad enfatizzare la sontuosità della corte o piuttosto concepita per fornire ulteriori chiavi interpretative.

Parole chiave: intrattenimento musicale, romanzi in medio inglese, banchetti, simbolismo musicale

Abstract: In medieval romances, musical entertainment often holds centre stage, as yet another manifestation of courtly pomp. Horn players and drummers, fiddlers, crowd players and harpers, organists and bagpipers, all play together to construct a musical accompaniment that is meant to enhance the merriment of the court. Long lists of different instruments appear to be carefully designed to convey the sumptuousness and harmony of the court. If on the one hand this might be used as a mere rhetorical device of amplification, on the other, it might serve a narrative function. This paper thus aims to analyse the representation of the musical entertainment in Middle English romances in order to understand whether specific selections of different instruments were merely used to emphasise the lavishness of the court or rather conceived to provide further interpretative keys.

Keywords: musical entertainment, Middle English romances, banquet, music symbolism

Banquet scenes are almost ubiquitous in medieval romances and depicted as the quintessential performance of courtly entertainment. These events are perceived as synaesthetic in nature as they simultaneously solicit all senses: lavish delicacies, exotic spices, precious fabrics and bright settings were customarily portrayed as unmissable features of courtly pomp. Nevertheless, music was probably the leading actor of this flamboyant courtly stage. The formulaic nature of these descriptions might have originated in the careful orchestration of every single aspect of real courtly events. Therefore, it comes as no surprise that musical

entertainment as well followed a strict protocol. As soon as trumpet blasts announced the beginning of the banquet, all guests approached to wash their hands before eating¹. This habit almost retained a ritualistic quality, so much so that it came to be identified with a specific name: *corner l'eau*, literally, 'blow the water' (Bowles 1958: 43). Trumpets and drums then greeted each new course, whereas wind instruments entertained the chattering guests during the consumption of delicacies of unsurpassed refinement (Bowles 1958: 42-45)². A fanfare finally marked the conclusion of the banquet and the removal of the tables from the hall to make room for further music and dance. Minstrels' voice performances or solos on string instruments were also typical courtly entertainments (Bowles 1958: 46-49)³.

The rigid planning characterising this incredible display of *grandeur* and exclusiveness could not but reverberate in the literary genre that most enthusiastically celebrated courtly life: romance. According to Christopher Page, «the lists of musical entertainments usually adhere to a constant plan: they generally follow a meal and are therefore often signalled by some such formula as “when the meal was over...”, or “when the table cloths were lifted away...”». However, given their formulaic nature, these passages could only partially be considered reliable descriptions of real practice in medieval banquets (1984-5: 16). They might rather have been conceived to perform a narrative function.

Although in the Middle Ages musical instruments generally retained a specific symbolism in both secular and religious contexts, their allegorical function was often tailored to meet narrative requirements. Far from being a mere rhetorical device meant to celebrate the lavishness of the court, the representation of musical entertainments might thus have been aimed at drawing the audience's attention

¹ As expected, this practice is described in romances as well. For instance, in the late fourteenth-century *Richard Coer de Lyon*, one of the several banquet scenes is conveniently introduced by the description of the guests washing their hands: «Trumpes blewen, tabours dasschen, / Mete was greythid, they gunne to wasschen» (*Richard Coer de Lyon*, ll. 4643-4644, ed. Larkin 2015) [The trumpets were blown, the drums rolled / food was prepared, they began to wash (their hands)]. Unless otherwise specified, all translations are mine.

² *Richard Coer de Lyon* offers yet another example of this habit: «Fro kechene com the fyrste cours, / With pypes and trumpes and tabours» (*Richard Coer de Lyon*, ll. 3453-3454, ed. Larkin 2015) [From the kitchens came the first course / with pipes, trumpets and drums].

³ Although it is impossible to determine the extent to which these descriptions were meant to be realistic, the French romance *Cleriadus et Meliadice* offers an example of the order of the performances in medieval banquets: an ensemble of wind instruments accompanied the dancers, whereas young squires were subsequently expected to sing with no musical accompaniment, «et, en ce point, vont venir les menestriers si commencent à corner. [...] la feste dura longuement et, quant ilz eurent assez dancé en ceste stat, les menestriers cesserent si se print [on] à dancier aux chançons et là veissez homes et femmes bien dancier et chanter» (*Cleriadus et Meliadice*, ed. Zink 1984: 15). [The minstrels began to play loud wind instruments. [...] the entertainment lasted a long time. And when they had danced their fill, the minstrels ceased and they began to sing.] (Page 1982: 443).

on specific characters or crucial passages in the narrative. An in-depth analysis of the depiction of musical entertainment in Middle English romances might reveal the extent to which the allusion to specific instruments was meticulously designed to provide further interpretative keys. Large ensembles will be attentively scrutinised to understand whether the instruments mentioned were randomly listed with the sole purpose of conveying an effect of amplification or if they were carefully selected and ordered according to their symbolism. The analysis will then focus on specific instrument types. Wind and percussion instruments will be analysed together, due to their frequent co-occurrence in almost formulaic clusters, whereas string instruments will be separately examined, due to their well-established symbolic significance.

1. Rhetorical and aural amplification: the description of large ensembles

In the late Middle Ages, instruments were usually grouped according to their sonority into loud, *haut*, instruments, such as horns, shawms, trumpets, drums and low, *bas*, instruments, such as rotes, harps, vielles, rebecs, psalteries, flutes (Bowles 1954: 119-120; Buckland 2003: 81)⁴. There seems to have been a preference for contrasting sounds, so much so that low and loud instruments were often played together (Reese 1960: 481). This classification also entailed the identification of the appropriate context of use for each category. In the late fourteenth-century allegorical poem *Les Eschéz d'Amour*, the description of the Garden of Delight is supplemented by a comprehensive list of the instruments used to entertain Delight, the God of Love, as well as their entourage. The anonymous author not only classifies the instruments according to the intensity of their sound, but also creates a situational association: loud instruments are more suitable for dance, whereas low instruments for intimate contexts. He then broadens his view so as to encompass the effects of the resulting music on the audience. Thus, the sounds of trumpets, drums and bagpipes can immediately elicit joyful feelings, whereas that made by string instruments is described as *doulce*, 'sweet' (*doulcez nottez*). If on the one hand this combination of loud and soft instruments might mirror the medieval preference for contrasting sounds, on the other they are not randomly mixed, but rather orderly listed as to create an alternation of low – loud – low sounds.

La ouïst on sonner vielles
Et harpes excellentement
Et psalterions ensement,

⁴ The distinction between loud and low instruments was not limited to volume, but rather involved the field of social rank as well. For instance, trumpets were commonly associated with aristocratic/heraldic use (Buckland 2003: 81).

Ghisternes, rebeblez et rotez,
 Qui faisoient moult doucezes nottez,
 Leüs qui sont de plus grant ton.
 Orguez en main y oïst on,
 Et citoles meïsmement,
 Qui sonnoient moult doucement,
 Chyffonyes et monocordes
 Et maint aultre instrument de cordes,
 Telz c'on ne sceuist mieulx penser.
 Et quant il vouloient danser
 Et faire grans esbattemens,
 On sonnoit lez haulz instrumens,
 Qui mieulx aux dansez plaisoient
 Pour la grant noise qu'ilz faisoient.
 La peuist on oïr, briefment,
 Sonner moult de renouïsement
 Trompez, tabours, tymbrez, naquaires,
 Cymballes, dont il n'est mes guaires,
 Cornemusez et chalemelles
 Et cornes de fachon moult belles.
 Et puis aultrefois reprenoient,
 Quant mendre noise demandoient,
 Flasozez fleütez et douchaines,
 Qui sont moult douces et moult saines,
 Et telz aultrez instrumens bas
 Dont moult est plaisans li esbas.
 (*Les Eschéz d'Amour*, ll. 4300-4328, ed. Heyworth – O'Sullivan 2013:
 256-257)

[They heard playing hurdy-gurdies / and harps excellently / and psalteries in the same way, / guitars, and rotes / which made very sweet notes, / lutes which have a great tone, / and portative organs / and citoles in the same way / which sounded very softly / vielles and monochords / and many other stringed instruments / such as one did not know how to think better. / And when they wanted to dance / and have great merriment, / they sounded high instruments, / which were more pleasing to the dancers, / for the great noise they made. / You could quickly hear / the sound of what gives joy / trumpets, drums, tambourines, / cymbals, of which there are none, / bagpipes and chalumeaux / and horns in a very beautiful way. / And then in different circumstances / when they needed less noise / flutes and *douçaines* / which are very sweet and wholesome / and such other low instruments / whose entertainment is very pleasant.]

Significantly, the sound of flutes and *douçaines* is not only associated with sweetness, but also with wholesomeness, as though the harmony created by the resulting music could simultaneously lead to spiritual and physical wellbeing. Yet, unlike harps and string instruments in general, wind instruments are not usually

taken as symbols of harmony and good government. This can all too well demonstrate the extent to which any attempt at generalisation is undermined by the fluidity of these symbolic associations.

The polysemy characterising the names of several musical instruments appears to complicate the matter further. For instance, although the *douçaine* was supposedly a type of shawm, it is reported to have had a softer tone and a limited range, thus making it suitable for lower ensembles. According to Buckland, yet another distinction could be drawn in terms of use. Loud instruments usually performed in outdoor contexts, due to the intensity of the sound produced, whereas low instruments were perceived as more suitable for indoor entertainment (2003: 81). Yet, this distinction somehow appears to be undermined by the complexity of musical entertainment in the late Middle Ages. Although drums, trumpets, pipes and shawms were certainly typical in civic processions, they were by no means the sole instruments allowed to perform. For instance, in mystery plays, string instruments and portative organs are also recorded (Bowles 1961: 149; 160).

In his early fifteenth-century *Reson and Sensuallyte*, John Lydgate provides an expanded translation of the episode of the Garden of Delight from *Les Eschéz d'Amour*. Far from generating a cacophonous confusion of disparate sounds, the ensemble described produces a heavenly melody.

For ther wer rotys of Almanye
 And eke of Arragon and spayne,
 Songes, stampes, and eke daunces,
 Dyuers plente of plesaunces,
 And many vnkouth notys newe
 Of swiche folkys as lovde trewe,
 And Instrumentys that dyde excelle,
 Many moo than I kan telle:
 – Harpys, fythels, and eke rotys,
 Wel accordyng with her notys,
 Lutys, Rubibis, and geterns,
 More for estatys than taverns, –
 Orgnys, cytolys, monacordys.
 And ther wer founde noo discordys,
 Nor variaunce in ther sovns,
 Nor lak of noo proporsiouns,
 Ther was so noble accordaunce;
 And for folkys that lyst daunce
 Ther wer trumpes and trumpetes,
 Lowde shallys and doucetes,
 Passyng of gret[e] melodye,
 And floutys ful of armonye,
 Eke Instrumentys high and lowe

Wel mo than I koude knowe,
 That I suppose, ther is no man
 That aryght reherse kan
 The melodye that they made.

(Lydgate, *Reson and Sensuallyte*, ll. 5571-5597, ed. Sieper 1901: 146-147)

[For there were rotes from Germany / and also from Aragon and Spain / songs, estampie, and also different / dances full of merriment, / and many unknown new notes / of a truly loud kind, / and instruments that did excel, / many more than I can tell: / harps, fiddles and also rotes, / well harmonising their notes, / lutes, rebecs and gitterns, / more for great status than for taverns, / organs, citoles, monochords. / And there could be found no discord, / no variance in their sounds, / no lack of proportions, / there was so noble harmony, / and for people that wanted to dance / there were horns and trumpets, / loud chalumeaux and *douçaines*, / emanating great melody, / and flutes full of harmony, / and other instruments high and low / well more than I could know, / that I suppose there is no man / that can correctly report / the melody that they made.]

The audience is overwhelmed by an aural progression from low to loud instruments all playing together in a grandiose performance, where *proporsiouns* and *accourdaunce* guarantee the resulting harmony. However, one might argue that this ensemble is described as playing in a supernatural environment and might thus have been aimed at producing an effect of sublime happiness. The narrative function of this passage, as well as its highly symbolic overtones, might thus have overcome any desire for realism. One last thought should be given to the polysemic quality of the vocabulary related to musical instruments. In this context, *douçaines* are associated with loud sound, *lowde*, thus possibly implying that the instrument Lydgate had in mind was in fact some kind of louder shawm, rather than the *douçaine* described in his source text.

In the early-fourteenth century *Libro de Buen Amor* by Juan Ruiz, Archpriest of Hita (Ruiz, trans. Kane 1968: xiv), a list of as many as thirty instruments is provided. In the section devoted to the allegorical account of the lavish celebration for the return of Sir Love, a flamboyant parade is staged in his honour (Ruiz, ed. Corominas 1967: 475-477). The overwhelming predominance of string instruments – half the instruments mentioned are in fact string instruments – would somehow undermine the idea that low instruments were exclusively used indoor. One might argue that since this parade is part of an allegorical literary work, this list might have been meticulously designed to meet narrative and symbolic requirements. However, as stressed by John Esten Keller, «Juan Ruiz was familiar with all the musical instruments of his time, and his descriptions of the many he used or understood is detailed. Indeed, the *Libro de Buen Amor* could serve alone as the basis for a study of medieval musical instruments» (Ruiz, trans. Kane 1968: liii). The comprehensive study on medieval civic procession carried out by Edmund Bowles definitely seems to confirm

that low and loud instruments were played simultaneously in these flamboyant outdoor events as well (1954: 135). However, in spite of Bowles' reassurances about the compresence of contrasting sounds, when dealing with the description of musical entertainment in literary contexts, a note of caution should still be sounded, as «there is no way of knowing which instruments were in common use and which were not, and mediaeval writers must in many cases have listed – for reasons of completeness or symbolism – instruments which were rarely heard» (Rastall 1974: 199).

The early-fourteenth-century *Guy of Warwick* contained in the Auchinleck Manuscript (Edinburgh, NLS, Adv. 19.2.1) is a loose translation of an Anglo-Norman romance, written in England roughly one century earlier. The eponymous hero's story might be divided into two parts: the first, in couplets, reports the deeds that Guy performs in order to become the most renowned knight in the world and thus conquer the heart of the Earl of Warwick's daughter, Felice. The second, in stanzas, begins with the celebrations for the longed-for marriage. Yet, this colourful representation of happiness and delight is immediately followed by the moment of revelation in which Guy realises that his life has been sinfully spent in search of personal renown. His subsequent feats will thus be solely prompted by the love of God. Considering the bipartite structure of the romance, the passage depicting the wedding celebrations might function as some sort of watershed by being simultaneously the happy ending of the first part and the initial situation from which the second is about to unfold. Given the centrality of this episode, the comparison between the Anglo-Norman description of the wedding celebrations and its Middle English rendition might uncover different narrative strategies. The thirteenth-century Anglo-Norman *Gui de Warewic* devotes some five lines to the description of the musical entertainment.

Les noces puis tenues unt,
 Quatre jurz grant joe funt:
 Assez i out des menestrers,
 Del realme les plus chiers,
 Bons arpeurs e vielurs,
 Roturs, gigurs e tympanurs,
 De totes maneres i out juleurs
 (*Gui de Warewic*, ll. 7339-7345, ed. Ewert 1933: 25)

[Then they held the wedding-feast and celebrated for four days. There were plenty of minstrels, the best in the kingdom – good harpers, players on viols and rotes, fiddlers and tambourine-players. There were all kinds of jugglers. (*Boeve de Haumtone and Gui de Warewic*, transl. Weiss 2008: 179)]

The five-instrument ensemble depicted thus appears entirely consistent with what is known of medieval musical performances. Although this passage is

characterised by a distinct predominance of *bas* instruments (*arpeurs*, *vielurs*, *roturs*, *gigurs*), *haut* instruments are not entirely neglected, as a tambourine player (*tympanurs*) is reported to have provided accompaniment for the other musicians.

The Middle English rendition of this list of musical instruments reveals subtle and yet rather consequential differences.

Þer was trumpes & tabour,
 Fiþel, croude & harpour
 Her craftes for to kiþe;
 Organisters & gode stiuous,
 Minstrels of mouþe & mani dysour
 To glade þo bernes bliþe.
 Þer nis no tong may telle in tale
 Þe ioie þat was at þat bridale
 (*Guy of Warwick*, ll. 1883-1890, ed. Zupitza 1883: 394-396)

[There were horn players and drummers, fiddlers, crowd players and harpers, organists and skilled bagpipers, story-tellers and many jesters; all were there to show their skills, to please those people. It is impossible to report in words the joy that characterised that wedding feast.]

The original list appears to have been supplemented with three additional instruments: two wind instruments – trumpets and bagpipes – and the portative organ. The core of string instruments is conversely almost unchanged: the Anglo-Norman *vielurs*, *roturs*, *gigurs*, and *arpeurs* are in fact rendered by the Middle English *fiþel*, *croude* and *harpour*. Both the Middle English «tabour» and the Anglo-Norman *tympanour* correspond to the players of different types of small drums. According to Alison Wiggins, these lists appear to have been almost a cliché in medieval romances; however,

what is unusual is the length and detail of this description. Not only are several elements combined but these are repeated and extended, so an unusually long list of seven instruments is given (there are players on horns, drums, fiddle, crowd, harp, organs, bagpipes) and the narrator asserts that there is “al maner menstracie” and then, again, that there is “al maner of gle” (*Guy of Warwick*, ed. Wiggins 2004: 130-131).

The Middle English redactor might thus have wanted to convey an effect of amplification (*amplificatio*) not only in terms of sound, but also of abundance⁵.

⁵ «Lengthy catalogues of instruments are conventional in medieval narrative poetry, and generally communicate an atmosphere of festive abundance rather than a mimetic account of specific performing ensembles» (Hout 1989: 69).

This hypothesis might find support in another change made by the Auchinleck redactor as compared to his Anglo-Norman source text: the duration of the celebrations. In the Middle English version, they are reported to have lasted ten additional days as compared to the Anglo-Norman original. This expansion could hardly be dismissed as a scribal mistake; it might rather have been meticulously designed to exaggerate the courtly splendour, possibly to appeal to a patron's taste⁶.

However, even longer lists of instruments are not unusual in a romance context. For instance, in his twelfth-century romance *Érec et Enide*, Chrétien de Troyes describes the celebrations for the marriage of Érec and Enide as featuring a large ensemble of ten instruments.

Quant la corz fu tote asanblee,
 N'ot menestrel an la contree
 qui rien seüst de nul deduit,
 qui a la cort ne fussent tuit.
 An la sale molt grant joie ot,
 Chascuns servi de ce qu'il sot.
 Cil saut, cil tunbe, cil anchante;
 Li uns sifle, li autres chante,
 cil flaüte, cil chalemele;
 cil gigue, li autres viele;
 puceles querolent et dancent;
 trestuit de joie fere tancent.
 Rines n'est qui joie puisse fere
 Ne cuer d'ome a leesce trere,
 Qui as noces ne fust le jor.
 Sonent tinbre, sonent tabor,
 muses, estives et freteles
 et buisines et chalemeles!

(Chrétien de Troyes, *Érec et Enide*, ll. 1983-2000, ed. and trans. Miland-Bove – Obry 2022: 234-235)

[When they all gathered, no minstrel of the country with some training in the art of entertaining was missing from the court. Great joy reigned in the hall, everyone showed off their talents. One jumped, another fell, one performed some magic tricks; one whistled, another sang, one played the flute and another the reed-pipe; one played the gigue and another the fiddle; young girls danced in carols; all competed in gaiety. Nothing that could bring joy to one's heart was missing on that

⁶ Since the Auchinleck Manuscript might have been conceived to celebrate the Beauchamp family – though no final evidence has ever been uncovered as to the identity of this manuscript's patron – the extension of the feast might have been aimed at emphasising the grandeur of the family of the Earls of Warwick (Turville-Petre 1996: 106).

wedding day. Tambourines and drums resounded; bagpipes and panpipes, trumpets and reed-pipes played (in the hall)].

Flutes, reed-pipes, gígues, fiddles, tambourines, drums, two types of bagpipes (*muses* and *estives*), panpipes and trumpets all contribute in creating an extraordinary sensory experience. As stressed by Page, «the cumulative effect of the passage is to evoke a feast so abundant and so luxurious that it almost defies description in discursive terms» (1984: 16).

In his late-twelfth or early-thirteenth century *Le Bel Inconnu*, Renaud de Beaujeu even surpasses Chrétien's *Érec* in terms of abundance by listing sixteen different loud and low instruments. Unlike the description offered by Lydgate, the instruments are not listed so as to create an aural crescendo, but rather paired by similar or contrasting sounds. Hence, wind and string instruments are grouped so as to form some sort of unit: «estive» / «vièle»; «muses», «saltères» and «frétel».

L'un voit as fenestres harper,
L'autre delès celui roter,
L'un estive, l'autre vièle,
Li autres gígile et calimèle,
Et cante cler comme seraine,
Li autres la citole maine,
Li uns entendoit au corner,
Et l'autres au bien flahuter;
Li un notoient lai d'amor;
Sonnent timbre, sonnent tabor;
Muses, saltères et frétel,
Et buissines et moinel

(Renaud de Beaujeu, *Le Bel Inconnu*, ll. 2867-2878, ed. Hippeau 1860: 102)

[He saw someone playing the harp at the window, / someone, next to him, played the rote; / someone the flute, / someone else the vielle, / someone the viola and the chalumeau / while singing with a clear mermaid's voice, / someone played the citole, / someone the horn, / someone else was masterfully playing the flute; / someone sang love *lais*; / while drums and tambourines, / musettes, psalteries and flutes, / trumpets and smaller horns resounded.]

Insular writers also appear to have drawn on this tradition. In the fourteenth-century Middle English Breton *lai Emaré*, the celebrations for the recovering of Lady Egaré are customarily accompanied by an ensemble mixing opposing sounds: percussion, wind and string instruments (*tabours*; *trommpus*; *sawtré*, *harpe* and *fydylling*).

Syr Kadore lette make a feste
That was fayr and honeste,
Wyth hys lorde, the kyng.

Ther was myche menstralsé,
 Trommpus, tabours and sawtré,
 Bothe harpe and fydyllyng.
 (*Emaré*, ll. 385-390, ed. Laskaya – Salisbury 1995: 164)

[Sir Kador organised a feast / that was noble and magnificent, / with his lord the king. / There was much musical entertainment, / trumpets, drums and psaltery, / both harp and fiddling]

Significantly, although this *lai* is characterised by two additional celebrations (the wedding of the king of Galys and Emaré, the final reconciliation), this is the sole instance of musical entertainment described. One might wonder whether the emphasis on this episode might have been driven by narrative requirements. The powerful Emperor Artyus had fallen in love with his beautiful daughter Emaré and had obtained a papal dispensation to marry her. Upon her refusal to accept him as her husband, he sets her adrift in a boat. After much wandering, she finally lands in Galys, where she is rescued by the king's steward Sir Kador. He takes her to his lord's castle and helps her recover. However, although this episode would have made a perfect happy ending for the Breton *lai*, it merely triggers further action. Emaré's loyalty and patience in enduring hardship will be tested again. Shortly after her marriage to the King of Galys, she is abandoned once more to her fate. The happy ending is sealed by the reconciliation of her family some six hundred lines later. Just as in *Guy of Warwick* the musical entertainment was possibly meant to draw the audience's attention on a crucial point in the narrative, so in the *lai* of Emaré, it is masterfully designed to highlight the initial situation of the second part of the story. The harmony represented by the string instruments is interrupted by drums and trumpets, harbingers of upcoming unrest.

Yet, in all the examples analysed, the instruments are not openly reported as playing together; nevertheless, their being juxtaposed in a single narrative passage conveys the impression of ensembles of magnificent might (Page 1984-1985: 16). In his fourteenth-century poem, *Remède de Fortune*, Guillaume de Machaut might offer further insight into the way these passages should be interpreted. After narrating his adventures to the lady of the castle, the young poet-lover is invited to join her sumptuous banquet, which is, needless to say, accompanied by rich musical entertainment. If on the one hand a list of more than thirty different instruments might at this point come as no surprise, it is the concluding emphasis on their playing together that might defy the modern sense of order and propriety⁷.

La firent meins divers acors;
 Car je vi la tout en un cerne

⁷ An impressive list of more than thirty different types of instruments can also be found in Machaut's *La Prise d'Alexandrie* (Machaut, ll. 1148-1174, ed. M.L. de Mas Latrie 1877: 35-36).

Violle, rubelle, guiterne,
 Leü, morache, micanon,
 Cytole, et le psalterion,
 Harpe, tabour, trompes, nacaires,
 Orgues, cornes, plus de dis paires,
 Cornemuses, flajos, chevretes,
 Douceinnes, simbales, clocettes,
 Tymbre, la fleüste brehaingne,
 Et le grant cornet d'Alemaingne,
 Flajos de Scens, fistule, pipe,
 Muse d'Aussay, trompe petite,
 Buissines, eles, monocorde
 Ou il n'a c'une seule corde,
 Et muse de blef tout ensemble.

[They played various harmonies, for there all in a circle I saw vielle, rebec, guitar, lute, Moorish guitar, small psaltery, cittern, and the psaltery, harp, tabor, trumpets, nakers, portable organs, more than ten pairs of horns, bagpipes, flutes, musettes, *douçaines*, cymbals, bells, timbrels, the Bohemian flute and the large German cornett, willow flutes, a fife, pipe, Alsatian reed pipe, small trumpet, buisines, a psaltery, a monochord (which has a single string), and straw pipe all together. (Guillaume de Machaut, *Remède de Fortune*, ll. 3962-3977, ed. Winsatt – Kibler 1988: 390-391)]

However, *asyndeton* is not the sole rhetorical device used to create an effect of amplification in terms of sound and sumptuousness of the court. Yet another strategy consists in emphasising the inadequacy of human language to convey the whole extent of the pleasure produced by music. For instance, in the thirteenth-century poem *La Mort Le Roi Artu*, the legendary king is reported to have sought hospitality at Morgan's castle. A sumptuous banquet is promptly prepared to welcome the royal guest. Shortly after the meal, King Arthur leaves the hall and enjoys the delight provided by the music played from an adjacent chamber.

Quant il orent mangié a grant plente tant comme il leur plot, li rois escoute et ot en
 une chambre qui esoit encoste de lui touz les diuers estrumenz dont il eust onques
 oi parler en sa vie; si sonoient tout ensemble li vn avec les autres si tres doucement
 qu'il n'avoit onques oie melodie que tant li fust douce ne plesanza a oir. (*La Mort
 Le Roi Artu*, ed. Frappier 1936: 46-47)

[When they had all eaten their fill, as much as they wished, the king lent his ear and, from an adjacent chamber, listened to the sound of all the different musical instruments he had ever heard of in his life. They were all playing together, each one with the others, so pleasantly that the resulting melody surpassed anything he had ever heard in sweetness and pleasantness.]

Although no specific instrument is mentioned, the author openly states that all of them were playing at the same time, thus essentially creating the most complete and ideally perfect ensemble of all. He also seems to imply that the greater the number of the instruments and the skill of the minstrels, the sweeter the resulting harmony. The verisimilitude of this description is irrelevant to the economy of the narrative, as it might have been carefully designed to depict a musical entertainment of supernatural perfection.

2. *Trumpes & tabour*: percussion and wind instruments in courtly and martial contexts

An in-depth analysis of the description of the musical entertainment in the previously mentioned *Guy of Warwick* reveals that in the Middle English version, the order of the performing instruments is inverted as compared to its source text. In the Anglo-Norman original, a sequence of four string instruments is closed by a tambourine, which is probably meant to provide some accompaniment. In the Middle English version, the same sequence is opened by trumpets and drums and closed by bagpipes, hardly an expected ensemble for a courtly banquet. *Trumpes*, *tabour* and *stives* might in fact seem more suitable for parades or military marches than for wedding celebrations. However, if on the one hand *split sounds* were favoured in the Middle Ages, wind, string and percussion instruments not only could potentially be played together, but their combination was even encouraged (Bowles 1958: 48), on the other the polysemy of their names appears to prevent any straightforward identification of the characteristics of the ensembles described. For instance, trumpets were certainly considered loud instruments and yet some of them were specifically conceived to be played indoors. The *buisine* was a large trumpet of metal pre-eminently used in military contexts and tournaments, though at times it could also be blown at wedding celebrations and festivals (Bowles 1954: 122). Small s-shaped trumpets were conversely almost exclusively used for indoor performances (Bowles 1954: 125). In Middle English, the word *trumpes* could be used to describe either type of instrument⁸. Nevertheless, the polysemy of musical terms does not seem to be limited to the insular context. In one early twelfth-century Occitan version of the song of Roland, *Ronsasvals*, the words *graile* and *corn* in fact appear to be almost interchangeably used for both Roland's Oliphant and any other trumpet-like instrument (Aubrey 1989: 134).

⁸ According to the *MED*, the meaning of *trumpes* in literary contexts ranged from «any of several trumpetlike horns in use in the Middle Ages» to «a flared hollow tube or pipe, water pipe; also, the windpipe of the crane». However, in fourteenth century records the instrument played at war, *trompette de guerre*, appears to have been some sort of *buisine*. (Rastall 1974: 191).

The intermingling of indoor and outdoor instruments is further emphasised in the fourteenth-century poem *The Carle of Carlisle*. The happy ending of the adventure of Gawain, Kay and Bishop Baldwin is celebrated with a magnificent banquet held by the newly retransformed Carle of Carlisle. King Arthur is amongst the guests; no effort should be spared. The display of courtly pomp thus goes as far as to include the use of silver trumpets to greet the guests at the main gate, «The trumpetts plaid att the gate, / With trumpetts of silver theratt» (*The Carle of Carlile*, ll. 463-464, ed. Hahn 1995: 387) [the trumpeters played at the gates with silver trumpets]⁹. Gawain has just succeeded in breaking the spell which had transformed the Carle into a heinous giant. An ensemble of sole string instruments can only emphasise the restoration of the courtly harmony.

There was all manner of minstrelsye –
Harpe, gyttorne, and sowtrye.
Into the hall the King was fett
And royallye in seat was sett.
(*The Carle of Carlile*, ll. 465-468, ed. Hahn 1995: 387)

[There were all types of entertainment / harp, gittern, psaltery. / Into the hall the King was escorted / and seated ceremoniously.]

The same ambiguity characterising wind instruments also appears to apply to percussion instruments. Timbrels and tambours are reported to have been played not only during banquets, but also in combination with trumpets in outdoor events. Similarly, horns and nakers were used as much to instil fear in the enemy's hearts on battlefields as to amuse the guests in courtly events (Bowles 1954: 123-124).

Therefore, the combination of trumpets and drums¹⁰ in the Auchinleck *Guy of Warwick* might trigger a broader reflection on the narrative function of these instruments. The analysis of the corpus of the Auchinleck romances reveals that the cluster *trumpes & tabour* is most commonly – but not exclusively – associated with military contexts. However, the key factor to determine whether their presence was really meant to supplement the narration with relevant interpretative keys is possibly their co-occurrence with other instruments. Before turning to the analysis of single instances, a note of caution should be sounded: metrical and stylistic reasons might also have influenced this cluster's popularity.

⁹ Significantly in this context the word *trumpetts* could refer to both the instrument and the person playing it.

¹⁰ Given the impossibility to determine with any certainty the types of wind and percussion instruments these redactors had in mind, they have been translated into modern English as trumpets and drums.

In one of the Middle English versions of the legend of King Horn, the early fourteenth-century *Horn Childe & Maiden Rinnild*, the sound created by trumpets and drums is twice evoked, in both courtly and military contexts. Horn's father, Hafeolf, is slain while bravely defending his country from Danish invaders. Horn is thus forced to leave his homeland and re-build his life at the court of King Hou-lac where he falls in love with the king's daughter, Rinnild. After having gained great renown in foreign lands, Horn finally comes back to restore his reputation and marry his beloved Rinnild. While approaching the court in disguise, he hears from the distance the piercing sound of trumpets and drums possibly played to celebrate the pre-arranged marriage of Rinnild with King Mogin.

When Horn fro fer herd glewe,
 Wiþ tabournes bete & trumppes blewe,
 Ozaines hem he ȝede.
 (*Horn Childe*, ll. 901-903, eds. Burnley – Wiggins 2003)

[When Horn heard the music from afar, / with the roll of drums and the blare of trumpets / he approached.]

A list of merely two instruments could hardly be considered an instance of rhetorical amplification; therefore, different reasons might have prompted the choice of such an ensemble. One of Horn's friends, Wiard, is reported to have been simultaneously gathering military support to Horn's cause. Horn has in fact set his eyes on a much bigger prize: his father's rightful inheritance. More battles are to follow. Therefore, although the context is admittedly not a military one, trumpets and drums somehow appear to preannounce the course of the future events.

A similar instance can be detected in yet another story of unlawful disinheritance and subsequent reconquest of titles and properties, that of Beues of Hamtoun. The young Beues is forced to flee the court as his father has been ambushed and treacherously slain by his mother's lover. His departure is made all the more heart-breaking by the music emanating from his native court.

He beheld toward þe tour,
 Trompes he herde and tabour
 And meche blis.
 (*Beues of Hamtoun*, ll. 382-384, eds. Burnley – Wiggins 2003)

[He looked at the tower, / he heard trumpets and drums / and much happiness.]

Once again, although *trompes* and *tabour* admittedly appear in a courtly context, they might be taken as omens of future unrest, as Beues' life will be all spent in fight.

The second instance of this ensemble that can be detected in *Horn Childe* is clearly related to the military context. Shortly after the wedding celebrations, Horn in fact sets off in order to reconquer his father's possessions in Northumberland.

When þai hadde eten þan were þai boun,
 Wiþ spere oloft & gonfainoun,
 Al armed were þo bold.
 Wiþ trump & tabourun out of toun,
 Þus þai redde þe riȝt roun,
 Ich man as he wold.
 (*Horn Childe*, ll. 1069-1074, eds. Burnley – Wiggins 2003)

[When they had eaten then they made themselves ready with spears and the banners lifted, in full armour, they looked so bold. With trumpets and drums out of the town, they performed the right tune, each man as he could.]

Trump & tabourun thus mark the pace of the marching troops¹¹. Similarly, in the Middle English version of the first part of the French Vulgate Cycle, *Of Arthur and of Merlin*, horns and drums are reported to have been played before and during the battle between King Arthur and King Rion.

Passed was þe dayspringing,
 Þe hote sonne was schininge
 Þo bigan kniȝtes rideing,
 Trumpes blowen, tabours dassing,
 Þer was fleinge & wiþstanding,
 Tireing, togging & ouerþroweinge;
 Of Sarrazins in litel stounde
 Mani þousand was frust to grounde.
 (*Of Arthur and of Merlin*, ll. 8799-8806, ed. Macrae-Gibson 1973: 341-342)

[The dawn had passed, the hot sun was shining, so the knights began to ride, trumpets were blown, drums were rolled, some were fleeing, some were standing their ground, some were fighting, some were taken to the ground and overcome. In little time, many thousand Saracens were killed.]

Þe trumpeing & þe tabouringe
 Dede togider þe kniȝtes flinge,

¹¹ The martial use of these musical instruments can also be detected in another romance from the Auchinleck Manuscript, *King Richard*, where «tabours & trumpes» (*King Richard*, l. 997, eds. Burnley – Wiggins 2003) are played to announce the mounting of the final all-out assault on the walls of Acre.

Þe kniȝtes broken her speren
 On þre, þai smiten & toteren;
 (*Of Arthur and of Merlin*, ll. 9165-9168, ed. Macrae-Gibson 1973: 351)

[Trumpets and drums / together called the knights to arms / the knights broke their spears / in three, they stroke and tore (the enemies' armours apart)]

And yet, the third instance in which *trumpes* and *tabour* are mentioned together in *Of Arthur and of Merlin* is definitely not in a war context, but rather during the courtly celebrations in which King Leodagan's daughter, Guinevere, falls in love with Arthur.

Þer were trumpes & fipelers
 & stiuours & tabourers,
 Þai eten & dro[n]ken & made hem glade
 & þo þai were al glad made
 Þe cloþes weren vp ydrawe
 & þai weschen so it was lawe.
 (*Of Arthur and of Merlin*, ll. 6557-6562, ed. Macrae-Gibson 1973: 283)

[There were horn players and fiddlers, bag pipers and drum players. They ate and drank and enjoyed themselves and after that, their clothes were removed and they washed themselves as it was customary.]

However, in this case, *trumpes* and *tabours* do not merely co-occur to form a proper cluster, but are rather paired with different instruments, namely fiddles and bagpipes respectively. The first couple is characterised by the uneasy combination of contrasting sounds, whereas the second creates that same martial atmosphere depicted above. Once again, this survey of musical instruments could hardly have been aimed at creating an effect of rhetorical amplification, since it consists of merely four items. It might rather have been conceived to be interpreted in the light of the endless strife characterising the whole romance. King Arthur is in fact forced to fight not only against those lords opposing his claim to the throne, but also against the Saracen invaders threatening Leodagan's lands. Significantly, this banquet scene functions as some sort of initial situation from which this crusading enterprise, probably the culmination of King Arthur's early military career, is about to begin.

In a military context, trumpets and drums are at time also accompanied by other high instruments aimed at both inflaming the troops' spirits and scaring the enemies. In the fourteenth-century poem *Otuel and Roland*, Roland, Oliver and Ogier come across a large army of more than six thousand Saracens. The enemies threateningly deploy to the sound of *chymbys* and *chynoures*. The three Christian paladins are forced to face them all.

He herde trumpes and tabeures,
 Hornes, chymbys, and chynoures.
 Somdel they were afryght.
 (*Otuel and Roland*, ll. 880-882, eds. Melick – Fein – Raybin 2019)

[He heard trumpets and drums, / horns, chimes, cymbals. / They were quite afraid]

Interestingly, in the Anglo-Norman source text *Otinel*, the Saracen army is merely accompanied by trumpets and horns, «Oient les corns, les busines suner» (*The Anglo-Norman Otinel*, l. 827, eds. Fein – Raybin 2019) [They hear horns and trumpets]. The addition of chimes and cymbals might well have been driven by metrical and stylistic reasons, as the Middle English redactor needed a rhyming word in *-es* to fulfil the requirements of the 12-line tail-rhyme stanza; nevertheless, it might also have stemmed from a desire for amplification. After all, in the Anglo-Norman original, the Saracen army is described as consisting of fifteen hundred men, whereas the Middle English translation reports four times that number¹².

The late-fourteenth-century Middle English Arthurian romance *Sir Gawain and the Green Knight* begins with a courtly setting strongly reminiscent of that described in *Guy of Warwick*. It is Christmas time and the legendary king is holding a magnificent banquet at which the guests are entertained by musical interludes. As was customary in the late Middle Ages, trumpets and drums announce the arrival of any new course. And yet, the description of musical entertainment is somehow disorienting, as the sole instruments mentioned appear to be pipes, or possibly bagpipes, drums and trumpets: an ensemble more suitable for a military march than for a banquet.

Ben þe first cors come with crakkyng of trumpes,
 Wyth mony baner ful bryzt þat þerbi henced;
 Nwe nakryn noyse with þe noble pipes,
 Wylde werbles and wyzt wakned lote,
 Þat mony hert ful hize hef at her towches.
 (*Sir Gawain and the Green Knight*, ll. 116-120, ed. Andrew – Waldron 2007: 212)

[Then the first course came with a blaring of trumpets, resplendent with many a banner that hung from them; there was a new sound of drums with the noble pipes, wild and piercing trills roused echoes, so that many hearts rose very high at their strains.]¹³

¹² For further discussion on the use of wind and percussion instruments in crusading contexts, see Page (1990: 482).

¹³ All translations from *Sir Gawain and the Green Knight* are taken from the digital prose translation included in Andrew – Waldron's 2007 edition.

As mentioned before, the poet's choice is peculiar not only due to the instrument selection, but also to their little variety, as crowded ensembles were believed to mirror the sumptuousness of the court.

The thirteenth-century writer Bartholomaeus Anglicus devotes an entire chapter of his encyclopaedic work, *De Proprietatibus Rerum*, to the description of the qualities that feasts should possess. One of his points is unsurprisingly devoted to music.

Octavum est cantorum et instrumentorum musicorum iocunditas. Sine enim cithara vel symphonia non solent coenae nobilium celebrari. *Luce XV*: cum audisset vocem, et cetera. (Bartholomaeus Anglicus 1491: VI. 23)

[The eighth is the merriment of the singers and the music instruments. In fact, aristocratic suppers are not served without harp or hurdy-gurdy. About light .15.: after having listened to the voices et cetera.]

In his view, no courtly meal should be consumed without the appropriate musical entertainment provided by voices, harps and hurdy-gurdies. Yet, in John Trevisa's Middle English translation, singers' voices are replaced with bagpipes, «þe eiȝthe is mirþe of song and of instrumentis of music. Noble men visiþ not to make soperes wiþout harpe oþir simphone, *Luce 15*^o: Whanne he herde þe symphonyand þe cornemuse, et cetera», [the eight is the delight of songs and music instruments. No noble man should have dinner with no accompaniment by harp or hurdy-gurdy, *Luce 15*^o: When he heard the hurdy-gurdy, the bagpipe] (Bartholomaeus Anglicus 1975: 330-331). The omission of bagpipes in the Latin original is entirely consistent with what the thirteenth-century author reports of their use towards the end of his treatise. In Bartholomaeus Anglicus' view, these instruments were not customarily associated with courtly entertainment, but rather with funeral marches and laments, «and was somtyme an instrument of deole and sorwe þat men vsede in office and sepulture of dede men» (Bartholomaeus Anglicus 1975: 1390) [And was anciently an instrument of mourning and sorrow that people used at the funerals and for the burials of the dead]. Nevertheless, Trevisa's substitution might not have stemmed from a translation mistake, but rather from the desire to make the account consistent with his own experience or with what was known to be the current fashion in terms of courtly feasts (Sachs 1980: 332). Therefore, the sole mention of bagpipes, drums and trumpets in a courtly environment cannot be used as evidence of the Gawain-poet's intention to provide a specific portrait of King Arthur and his court. Nevertheless, if one considers this passage in the light of what the author reports of the young king's personality a few lines earlier, this description takes on new shades of meanings. The military undertones alluded by the instrument choice would in fact perfectly match Arthur's *childegered*, 'puerile', attitude.

He watz so joly of his joyfnes, and sumquat childgered:
His lif liked hym lyzt, he louied þe lasse

Auþer to longe lye or to longe sitte,
 So bisied him his zonge blod and his brayn wyld.
 (*Sir Gawain and the Green Knight*, ll. 86-89, ed. Andrew – Waldron
 2007: 210)

[He was so lively in his youthfulness, and somewhat boyish. He loved an active life; he did not care much for lying in bed or sitting long, he was so agitated by his young blood and his restless mind.]

Arthur and his knights are depicted as somehow unable to control their youthful ebullience. Their inability to stay away from battlefields almost seems to imply that their very identity is solely based on renown and knightly deeds. They seem to be haunted by the need to prove to themselves they are worthy of their place amongst Arthur's knightly élite. The accompaniment chosen by the Gawain-poet to describe Arthur's warlike spirit might cast yet another shade of ambiguity on the King's ability to rule (van Schaik 2005: 38-61). The poem in fact seems to question whether a king whose judgement is blurred by the provocations of an intruder could in fact be a good king. Arthur immediately loses his temper and is ready to jeopardise his throne and crown in order to defend his honour. His personal interest has definitely overcome the common weal. The death of a king should not be considered as a mere private disgrace, but rather as a national threat, since it exposes the reign to instability and possibly to civil war. Since string instruments are taken as symbols of harmony and good government, their absence in the banquet entertainment might not be accidental or prompted by metrical and stylistic requirements, but rather intended to emphasise Arthur's shortcomings as a ruler.

3. *Sotell, sawtre, herpe* and *fidyll*: the skills of good knights and kings

If on the one hand trumpets, drums and bagpipes are certainly common in battle scenes, string instruments are not usually associated with military contexts. Once again, *Horn Childe* might demonstrate that, when it comes to meeting narrative requirements, the symbolism of musical instruments could overcome any desire for realism. At the news of a new Viking invasion, Hafeolf is forced to interrupt a *lai* abruptly (Putter 2012: 340). In order to make themselves ready for the upcoming fight the king and his army need a different kind of *play*. It might be impossible to determine whether *anoþer* should be interpreted as an additional *play* or a *play* belonging to a different genre, thus possibly accompanied by a different set of musical instruments¹⁴.

¹⁴ *Play* entails a wide range of meanings: 'merriment', 'disport', 'joy', 'game', 'martial play', 'music', 'music making', 'a theatrical play or performance', 'story', 'story-telling', etc. Significant-

He bad þe harpour leuen his lay
 ‘For ous bihoueþ anoþer play,
 Buske armour & stede.’
 He sent his sond niȝt & day
 Also fast as he may,
 His folk to batayl bede.
 (*Horn Childe*, ll. 157-162, eds. Burnley – Wiggins 2003)

[He asked the harper to stop his lay / ‘For we now need a different music, / take the armours and the steeds!’ / He sent his message by night and day / as fast as he could / he summoned his people to fight.]

For instance, in Wace’s *Roman de Rou*, a minstrel, one Taillefer, is reported to have sung the *Song of Roland* in order to raise the army’s spirit before the Battle of Hastings¹⁵. Therefore, Hafeolf’s new *play* might have also consisted in a piece of heroic poetry, a *geste*. The impossibility of determining what kind of *play* Hafeolf might have requested – a *geste*? a *romauunce*?, a *lai*? – can only emphasise the limits inherent in any attempt to find a straightforward definition of the characteristics of these genres and thus their appropriateness to specific contexts.

The emphasis on the use of the harp raises an entire network of intertextual allusions all revolving around the idea of good government, as this instrument is taken to be the very symbol of the perfect harmony in the realm (Hynes-Berry 1975: 669)¹⁶. King David, Sir Orfeo and Sir Tristrem all find their righteous place in the Auchinleck collection, each in a text exclusively devoted to him. However, although both Hafeolf/Horn and Orfeo share equal musical talent, their ability as leaders appears substantially different. Orfeo lacks both their military and political skills, as he is first incapable of setting up a fight to save his wife from the Fairy King and then he even abandons his realm out of grief at the loss of her. Therefore, in the context of *Sir Orfeo*, the harp represents a different set of values. It should be interpreted as a powerful civilising tool that could bring harmony and peace even amongst the most hostile creatures of all. In the economy of the narrative, Orfeo does not need to be a skilful military leader, as he already possesses the sole instrument that can succeed where the armies of men fail: his harp. The

tly, *lai* as well means ‘story’ or ‘song’, as well as «a short narrative poem of love, adventure, etc., to be sung and accompanied on instruments, especially the harp». *MED* = *Middle English Dictionary*.

¹⁵ «Taillefer, qui mult bien chantout, / sor un cheval qui tost alout, / devant le duc alout chantant / de Karlemaigne e de Rollant, / e d’Oliver e des vassals / qui morurent en Rencevals» [Taillefer, a very good singer, rode before the duke on a swift horse, singing of Charlemagne and of Roland, of Oliver and of the vassals who died at Rencesvals.] (Wace, *Roman de Rou*, ll. 8035-8040, ed. Andersen 1877: 348-349).

¹⁶ Furthermore, although the *topos* of the ruler/harper is certainly not of insular invention, in Middle English romances, it became almost a cliché (Dickinson 2015: 201).

enchanting power of his music is in fact the weapon that allows him to rescue his beloved Heurodis and restore his position at the head of his realm (*Sir Orfeo*, eds. Laskaya – Salisbury 1995).

In *Horn Childe*, the Auchinleck redactor also describes the features of aristocratic education: a young noble should be skilled in arms, hunting, practising all the games in fashion at the time, as well as playing the harp and the horn.

Arlaund, þat al þewes coupe,
 Boþe bi norþ & bi souþe –
 In herd is nouȝt to hide –
 On hunting was him most coupe,
 For to blowe an horn wiþ mouþe
 & houndes lede biside;
 To harpe wele & play at ches
 & al gamen þat vsed is,
 & mo was in þat tide.
 (*Horn Childe*, ll. 37-45, eds. Burnley – Wiggins 2003)

[Arlaund was familiar with all kinds of things / this cannot be kept secret / he was most skilled at hunting, / blowing the horn with his mouth / and leading his hounds beside him; / harping well and playing chess / as well as all the games / that were popular at the time and even more.]

Arlaund is thus entrusted with teaching the young prince the nobles' ways. At this stage of the story, music does not hold centre stage, but is rather merely described as one amongst many abilities that a knight should possess. However, its symbolic meaning might not have been discarded altogether: Horn's ability to play the harp might in fact foretell his future greatness as a ruler.

In the fourteenth-century poem *Lybeaus Desconus*, Gawain's illegitimate son Wyndeleyne is reported to have been able to play not only the harp, but also the citole, psaltery and fiddle.

Wyndeleyne was his name;
 Wyde sprong his fame
 Est, west, northe and southe.
 Myche he couthe of game,
 Sotell, sawtre in same,
 Herpe, fidyll than wele he couthe.
 (*Lybeaus Desconus*, ll. 145-150, ed. Shuffelton 2008)

[Wyndeleyne was his name; / his fame was truly widespread / East, West, North and South. / He knew of entertainment, / he could play the citole and the psaltery together, / the harp and the fiddle.]

However, although as mentioned before the ability to play string instruments and particularly the harp was part of the standard aristocratic training not only in literary contexts, but also in real life (Bowles 1954: 127; Mainoldi 2001: 288), the emphasis on the number of different instruments Wyndeleyne could play might have been aimed at conveying the stature of the hero. Just as the long lists of instruments at courtly banquets conveyed a sense of magnificent might, so the variety of those played by the eponymous hero could reveal the extent of his accomplishments as a knight.

4. Conclusion

The examples above might have demonstrated the extent to which the descriptions of musical instruments could provide additional interpretative keys only in so far as they are deciphered in the light of the relevant romance context. Although wind and percussion instruments are reported to have been played in the courtly environment as well, the analysis of the instances of the cluster *trumpes & tabour* in several Middle English romances reveals that its martial quality might have been exploited to raise specific expectations in the audience. The synaesthetic quality of medieval banquets is further reinforced by the visual and aural description of the courtly entertainment. Long lists of instruments appear to be the most effective narrative and rhetorical device to convey an effect of amplification. However, since the resulting music is characterised by contrasting and yet consonant sounds, it appears to reflect the quality of extraordinariness typical of medieval romances. After all, musical accompaniment can only be attuned to the flamboyant world of courtly romances. The symbolism associated with musical instruments being heavily dependent on the context appears to weaken any generalisations. However, the selection of specific instruments as well as their listing in crowded ensembles cannot be considered as stemming from the eccentric taste of romance writers, but rather from sophisticated knowledge shared by both audience and authors. Courts and battlefields, hunting parks and tournaments all represent the stages before which the deeds of romantic knights unfold. Just as these worlds continuously intertwine, so the instruments providing the musical accompaniment for the heroes' adventures move from one context to the next in an endless chain of symbols and significances, thus essentially revealing yet another aspect of the complexity and sophistication of late medieval courtly culture.

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